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COMMUNITY-BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING INITIATIVES

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ABSTRACT

Language classes that use community-based learning have a lot of opportunities for them. They can boost motivation for language acquisition and improve student engagement by promoting creativity, collaboration, and active learning. These community-based, classroom-connected courses promote linguistic awareness, facilitate resource sharing, and address community needs. Students' transferrable skills are improved by providing them with the chance to work in practical settings. There is less of a gap between the community and the institution, and there is encouragement of language acquisition. This article is devoted to analysing and highlighting studies on language classes that use community-based learning and how they affect the learners' academic performances.

Keywords: *community, community-based learning, languages, language learning.*

INTRODUCTION

The Community Based Learning (CBL) or Community Learning approach has gained considerable popularity as an effective and creative pedagogic methodology since the 1990s. Third-level colleges across the United States have incorporated this type of participation in society as a core component of their curricula. Through CBL, students engage in community-based activities that address needs that have been

recognized by local groups. Students participate in these community-based activities as part of their credit-bearing university courses, as opposed to volunteering; this helps them comprehend the course material and improves their academic performance. When implemented properly, the community practice is thoughtful, well-structured, and advantageous to both the community and the student. Sighmon 1996, Eyler and Giles 1999, McIlrath and Mac Labhrainn 2007, Zlotkowski 1999, and other authors all note that there is a balance created between academic learning and community involvement, and that student learning crosses the classroom walls. While an exact number of community-based/service-learning courses are now being taught is unknown, Campus Compact, the umbrella organization for the method, includes over 1,100 colleges and universities with different students of over 6 million. Numerous studies have been conducted on the advantages of CBL, and generally speaking, researchers have shown that after taking a CBL course, students have improved comprehension of the course material and have a greater capacity for comprehending and relating to distinctions in others, increased self-awareness and self-assurance, and improved gratitude and dedication to volunteerism. In terms of academic performance (GPA, writing abilities, and critical thinking skills), values (commitment to activism and promoting ethnic understanding), self-efficacy, leadership (leadership activities, self-rated leadership ability, interpersonal skills), choice of a service career, and plans to engage in service after college, an ongoing investigation of the effects of CBL on students at UCLA found significant positive outcomes.

METHODS

Qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were employed while conduct this research. And according to Hellebrandt, individuals who enroll in a CBL course can gain other advantages beyond language acquisition. Extensive research demonstrates that the method enhances students' acquisition of culture in addition to their language proficiency. As for the cultural domain, CBL can effectively address multiculturalism and diversity addresses; additionally, it can raise students' cultural competency. Abbott and Lear have noted that community-based learning helps address

these needs. “Community Service Learning [CSL] allows for maximizing the methodological principles of language teaching: communicative language use in authentic situations, understanding of cultures different than one’s own, connections to other disciplines and access to new knowledge, comparisons among languages and cultures, and engagement with communities,” the authors of the article assert, “even though the requirements are demanding for everyone involved, the rewards, both short- and long-term, make it worthwhile.” 323 in Abbott and Lear (2009).

There are a number of benefits in utilizing CBL approach during lesson, namely:

✚ ***No generalization.***

It is expected by pupils receiving instruction in a classroom to apply newly acquired knowledge to various real-world scenarios. Do you have pupils who, although perfectly able to tell the time on one of those creative Musical timepieces, are utterly incapable of telling the time on a real clock? My friends, this results from a failure to generalize. When a learner realizes, he can only demonstrate a skill in a single place or with just one individual, it can be quite discouraging. The requirement for a pupil to generalize a skill is removed when we use CBL to teach it in a natural context. From the start, they are taught how to use their skills in a real-world situation.

✚ ***A greater understanding of the possibilities of individuals with disabilities is achieved through community-based training.***

We have the chance to show our community how to engage with those with disabilities through the example of teachers and paraprofessionals. We have the ability to showcase their immense potential. The incredible things we witness every day in our classrooms can be displayed to the community.

✚ ***Motivation.***

Community-based instruction has always motivated students who were not before. Students engage in activities from real life that are relevant to them through CBL. And they realize the reasoning behind acquiring the skills they have been practicing in class, and CBL is centered around their needs and talents.

✚ CBL -Research-based approach.

It's usually ideal to use evidence-based approaches, and CBL corresponds with IDEA legislative requirements.

RESULTS

Positive results for students are linked to CBL. According to some scholars (e.g., Medina & Gordon, 2014), language learners could benefit from CBSL even in cases where assessed gains were statistically small or marginal. Though these trends may be the result of writers or journal editors who have an interest in seeing more CBL work in language education, such positive outcomes of CBL would theoretically be expected given the correlation between language learning and immersion-like experiences with native speakers (Thompson, 2012). Practitioners can better understand and apply the results to their own work by closely examining the findings and paying attention to the data sources and CBL experience context.

Figure №1. Student results across a number of empirical research.

Different outcomes on students' language development was found in studies on linguistic outcomes. The authors showed that while students believed that CBL contributed to their language development, it is unclear how much CBL actually helped to actual language development and needs more research. Multiple investigations were recommended by every researcher who used proficiency tests or assessments to measure linguistic outcomes. They all argued in favor of closely coordinating CBL operations with the language objectives. However, the results on perceived language growth are not minor; Pelletteiri (2011), for example, argued that learning perception is a significant outcome that has been demonstrated to support actual language growth.

DISCUSSION

When practicing language skills, it is best to use real resources. Preference for authentic sources is one of the principles of directly based learning models. Authentic or naturally existing materials, things not created with language instruction in mind—are preferred when using experiential learning methodologies. remarkably, a student in an online television broadcast program said, “Our project is very interesting even though we don't have the opportunity to teach young children.” Our experiences have given us a great deal of experience. The creation of internet access broadcasts taught us the proper way to utilize words, especially while speaking. Since we deliver the show, it is crucial that you accurately spell and pronounces any English words or sentences. Students can take part in the course development process when an English course is being established locally using a community-based approach. Using and activating local resources for language learning was a common feature of the method. The goal of the course is for pupils to improve their language proficiency and familiarity with local culture, which fosters community participation. Local residents in the community were able to join the other participants during the course creation process. Collaboration was a necessary condition for the course to succeed, as was clear. Support from the community was essential for students to continue their projects when they went into the field to gather data. Students will be able to form cooperation and form relations.

CONCLUSION

Language classes that use community-based learning can have a lot of advantageous effects. For example, they can boost student interest in language acquisition and encourage higher levels of engagement with the material by promoting active learning, creativity, and teamwork. In order to increase language visibility and resource sharing, courses require students to act as language ambassadors in the community. Students' transferrable abilities are strengthened when they are given the chance to work in a practical setting. Positive attitudes towards language learning are promoted, and the gap between the community and the university is reduced.

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